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News & Views ▼ Learning ▼ Action ▼

Partnerships ▼ Heritage ▼ Events ▼

Venue Hire (<https://templeofpeace.wales/>)

WCIA Contributes to National Collections initiative 'Our Heritage, Our Stories' (OHOS)

Over Summer 2024, WCIA have enjoyed contributing to the UK-wide heritage initiative 'Our Heritage Our Stories' (<https://ohos.ac.uk/>), managed through Glasgow University alongside a range of partners, and funded through the AHRC (Arts & Humanities Research Council).

The programme supports heritage bodies UK-wide in moving 'Towards a National Collection' (<https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk/>) – identifying ways to pool the digital resources, knowledge and

materials produced by heritage and community organisations across the 4 nations, using AI (Artificial Intelligence) to connect collections to reach the widest possible audiences – as one of WCIA’s student placements suggested, ‘a *google for heritage*’.

WCIA have contributed a case study of a small community organisation – in devolved Welsh context – with active heritage programming, but no ‘core funding’ or

external resourcing towards our public activities. ineligible for archives, libraries, tourism or other heritage funding streams. How can / do similar small organisations **harness the energies of volunteers** and community goodwill, towards preserving the UK's rich heritage? In a world where technology is developing exponentially and websites / resources replaced every few years, how can recently **digitised archival materials be made accessible to future** generations?

WCIA's 'OHOS' Project

A community grant through OHOS enabled:

- WCIA organised a series of **weekly 'Archiveathon' events** over 3 months, May to July 2024.

- These Wednesday afternoon 'drop in sessions' enabled WCIA to provide structured **support and mentoring** to Temple Friends and volunteers so they could work on a range of projects.
- The existing (part-time) Heritage Advisor staff member **capacity was supplemented** by a (temp) Archiveathons Assistant to support the Wednesday sessions / heritage research projects, plus one member of WCIA's international volunteering team in a supervisory / support capacity.
- This has enabled **onsite volunteering** to be brought under the banner of the '**Temple Friends**' support network,
- both to be supported going forward by the wider WCIA team, rather than reliant on the single Heritage staff member (who is part-time and not Cardiff-based).

- With this capacity in place, WCIA recruited one **student internship**, working on updating our Hidden History publications for transfer to People's Collection Wales; and **8 student 'insights' placements**, each undertaking individual work experience activities and projects (see below for example outputs).
- **Archiveathon Events** were held weekly on Wednesday afternoons: May 1 (<https://www.wcia.org.uk/peace-heritage/mayday-in-the-peace-archives/>), May 8, May 15 (<https://www.wcia.org.uk/events/archiveathon2024-may-15/>), May 22, May 29, June 5, June 12, June 19, June 26, July 3, July 10, July 17 and July 24.
- Ongoing over Autumn 2024, WCIA are working with the National Library of Wales / People's Collection Wales team on production of a short report exploring '**Digital Directions**' – using WCIA's case

study to offer insight towards current challenges of online collections management and volunteer participation, for staff and trustees of small organisations.

- WCIA worked with PCW to separate our Archives from 1 into 3 clearer accounts (WCIA Peace Archives, WW1 Book of Remembrance, Women's Peace Appeal), with a new navigation and collections structure for each.
- WCIA **Peace Archives** homepage has been updated.

OHOS Supported Project Outputs

Redesigned Hidden Histories publications

(<https://www.wcia.org.uk/welsh-peacemakers-feature-articles/>) on

PCW:

- David Davies, Internationalist Founder of Wales' Temple of Peace
(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/items/2150306>)
- Wales' WW1 Book of Remembrance
(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/items/2150361>)
- Minnie James' Children's Collection
(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/items/2150326>)
- Women's Peace Petition of 1923-24
(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/items/2150371>)
- Architect of Peace – Sir Percy Thomas' Design of Wales Temple
(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/items/2150296>) to Peace
- Great and the Good – Opening of Wales' Temple of Peace
(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/items/2150336>)
- 'A New Mecca' – the Story of Wales Temple of Peace
(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/items/2150276>)

Friends of Wales' Temple of Peace and Peace Garden

- [Temple Friends home \(https://www.wcia.org.uk/temple-friends/\)](https://www.wcia.org.uk/temple-friends/)
- Temple Friends [Volunteering projects \(https://www.wcia.org.uk/peace-heritage/placement-projects/\)](https://www.wcia.org.uk/peace-heritage/placement-projects/)
- Peace Gardening Bees

Supporting Information for Volunteers

- View [May-July 2024 Placement Projects \(https://www.wcia.org.uk/2024-temple-placements/\)](https://www.wcia.org.uk/2024-temple-placements/) feature and [OHOS review \(https://www.wcia.org.uk/peace-heritage/ohos-feature/\)](https://www.wcia.org.uk/peace-heritage/ohos-feature/) article

- Volunteers 'How To' Guide
(<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1soag1pPGL07wAGs5FPjDQhyBJgPxZ1U>)
- Hidden Histories Toolkit (<https://www.wcia.org.uk/peace-heritage/hiddenhistories-toolkit/>) updated for online volunteers and community groups
- Updated Temple Archives Catalogue
(<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BF5273qLUJlWYwWwQNjDjDDPF83ZHI45N/edit?usp=sharing&oid=115069577066873557875&rtpof=true&sd=true>)
- The National Archives / TNA Discovery
(<https://discovery.nationalarchives.gov.uk/browse/r/h/A17848779>) portal uploaded with Temple Archives listings (for organisations WLNU, CEWC, UNA Wales, UN UK, FFHC, WCIA)

- Updated Temple Library Catalogue
(https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1X_c5hBVj-MtBlxqPM3925H0mxk_j3KpEBrJjifCuoz4/edit?gid=1253059025#gid=1253059025)
- Updated People's Collection Wales profile
(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/users/8498>)
- Updated WCIA Peace Archives
(<https://www.wcia.org.uk/archives-and-collections/>) home page

O H
O S

Our Heritage

Our Stories

(OHOS) UK

Programme

(<https://ohos.ac.uk/>)

Placement

Blog -

Rhiannon

Day Heritage

(<https://www.wcia.org.uk/>)

Communicati

ons
news/wcia-
history/placement-

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internship

Placement

Blog -

Maryam

Ginwalla,

(<https://www.wcia.org.uk/>)

Recent

Heritage of
refugees

Refugees &

Peace
Garden
Memorials

Trail -
(<https://www.wcia.org.uk/peacegarden/>)
multiple
volunteers

Peace
Heritage

Helen
Thomas
Collection -

the Women
(<https://www.peoplesonlinecollections.com/items/2126861>)
of Greenham
Common

WW1 Book of
Remembranc

Jon Tomley
and the
Wales

National
(https://www.wcia.org.uk/memorial_to_mley_archives/)
Memorial
Association

Welsh
Women's

Archives on

People's

(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/users/8498>)

Collection

Wales

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Collection

(<https://viewer.library.wales/4642022#?xywh=-5592%2C-399%2C16014%2C7976>)

Wales

Peace

Petition on

(<https://www.peoplescollection.wales/users/115056>)

People's

Collection

Wales

(<https://www.wcia.org.uk/ohos/?print=print>)

Print Page

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